

A Correlative Study of the Rankings of IIMs based on National Institutional Ranking Framework (NIRF) and Citation Score

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Abstract

This study aims to examine the correlation between the rankings of Indian Institutes of Management (IIMs) based on two methods - the National Institutional Ranking framework (NIRF) and research output in terms of citation score. The study also aims to find out the top-cited authors from IIMs as well as their highly cited articles. Data for the study were collected from the official website of NIRF as well as Google Scholar. The study found that a total of 176157 citations were received by a total of 616 authors from twenty IIMs in which the Indian Institute of Management, Ahmedabad tops the list with 38594 total citations for 110 authors. Samir K Srivastava from IIM, Lucknow was the highly is identified as the most cited author among all the faculties across 20 IIMs for his paper Business Logistics/ Supply Chain Management with 4304 citations as on 07-08-2019. The correlation testing using Spearman's Rank Correlation Coefficient shows that at 95% confidence level there is significant correlation between the rankings of IIMs based on the two systems.

Keywords – Research Output; NIRF; NIRF Ranking; Indian Institute of Management (IIM); Citation Score.